

Key topics and challenges for creating community-led, inclusive, and sustainable housing: Grant-of-use cooperative housing in Catalonia

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1. Introduction

Over the last two decades, Barcelona has witnessed the emergence of a cooperative housing movement, known as the grant-of-use model, spurred by the socio-political context following the global financial crisis. This movement is part of a broader trend seen across Europe (Czischke et al., 2020; Tummers, 2016). Originating from grassroots efforts, it primarily seeks to address the pressing demand for affordable and adequate housing, while also responding to demographic shifts and the evolving housing needs within the population (Cabré & Andrés, 2018). The model has spread from the city of Barcelona to the rest of the territory, reaching smaller cities and rural areas (Tzika et al., 2023). The main characteristic of the grant-of-use cooperatives is the long-term right to use a home rather than own it, promoting non-speculative housing and positioning it as a collective endeavour. Residents actively participate in decision-making processes, reinforcing this model's collaborative nature (Avilla-Royo et al., 2021; Sostre Civic, 2017). By reconsidering the architectural typologies of housing through the incorporation of communal spaces and facilities, while parallelly creating more communal ways of living, these communities reshape the concept of dwelling and transform the social dynamics among residents (Lacol et al., 2018). Given the diverse project values and aims of the groups (affordability, neighbourhood revitalisation, ecological considerations, gender perspective), their demographic composition (age, gender, number of units), land access and tenure type (collective property, social housing), building characteristics (construction system, typology, rehabilitation), and community living (private and communal areas, activities), the approaches of each group and their collaboration with external entities can vary significantly (Lang et al., 2020). This article aims to identify the key challenges shaping the cooperative housing landscape in Catalonia and explore how different groups navigate these challenges.

2. Methodology

A mixed-method approach was selected as the most appropriate for this research, integrating both quantitative and qualitative methodologies. Initially, a comprehensive table was created, compiling information from 66 projects of cooperative housing in Catalonia, which are the ones in a more advanced phase, or at least having access to land. Information was gathered for each project on the following categories: location, collaboration, year, relation with the public, building characteristics, social characteristics of the groups, community, and neighbourhood. Five

projects were selected for the case study analysis, based on the diversity of their collaboration, building characteristics, and relation to the public sector.

A qualitative case study analysis was conducted, following the methodological guidelines of Groat & Wang (2013) and Yin (2018). The methodology follows a grounded theory approach (Corbin & Strauss, 1998), and more specifically what is known as abductive analysis (Tavory & Timmermans, 2014). Data collection spanned two distinct fieldwork periods: from September 2022 to April 2023 and later from September 2023 to April 2024, providing a comprehensive understanding across different project phases. Diverse methods were employed for data compilation, such as in-depth and semi-structured interviews with various stakeholders, comprising residents, architects, facilitators and professionals. These interviews offered multifaceted insights into individual perspectives and experiences. Additionally, the research gathered information through document analysis, encompassing materials from the participatory processes, documents generated by the residents' groups, and by the professionals and the intermediate organisations. This included architectural briefs, drawings, reports etc. Furthermore, data from public presentations and interviews with the projects' members were incorporated. Utilising these various sources provided the foundation for a comprehensive analysis, allowing for the triangulation of information and the exploration of diverse perspectives. The gathered data was analysed iteratively and classified into common themes.

3. Results

The data analysis has yielded significant themes that underscore key topics and challenges pertinent to the cooperative housing model operating under the grant-of-use. These results provide insights to identify focal points and propose mechanisms and practices aimed at achieving sustainable and inclusive housing outcomes.

3.1 Living in Community

One of the most important premises of the model is its aspiration to create a different way of living. The main motivation is the need to live in a community, countering the prevailing individualisation of contemporary living, which has exacerbated feelings of loneliness across wide segments of the population, contributing to what is commonly acknowledged as a 'crisis of care' (Fraser, 2016). Notably, a considerable proportion of residents within cooperative housing projects either live alone or belong to single-parent families. Acknowledgement of this communal ethos necessitates the active and intentional cultivation of interpersonal relationships within the group. Additionally, it entails the design of novel spatial configurations that reimagine the interplay between the private and the common spaces within new or adapted buildings (Jarvis, 2011). Finally, the concept of care also assumes significance within these initiatives, addressing a crucial contemporary issue with distinct gender dimensions (Jupp et al., 2019).

3.2 Collaborative process

Among the initiatives in Catalonia, three approaches have emerged concerning how groups realise their projects. Some opt for a self-managed model, retaining control over the entire process and coordinating all tasks internally. Others seek guidance from external entities while maintaining autonomy. A third category involves individuals becoming members of umbrella cooperatives, which initiate the projects and lead the process. Each of the three options offers distinct advantages and can cater to the diverse needs of different individuals or communities. While self-management affords greater autonomy for the group, it may prolong the timeline due to extensive involvement. Conversely, relying on external support can streamline the process but

might involve sacrificing some degree of control (Huisman & Czischke, 2023). Additionally, groups may form with the explicit goal of living together, commonly referred to as intentional communities, or they may assemble through waiting lists facilitated by external entities. Regardless of the formation method, groups inevitably encounter the need to integrate new members at some stage, an action which requires thoughtful management of member inclusion dynamics.

3.3 Diversity/ Inclusion

As the model continues to evolve, it has begun to embrace greater diversity, as groups with varying needs and identities initiate their projects. However, alongside this growth, concerns on inclusivity have emerged from the discussions within the collective spaces of the cooperative housing movement (Bresson & Labit, 2020). A recurring criticism is the relative homogeneity of the groups, often comprising residents with similar profiles and economic, cultural or social resources (Sørvoll & Bengtsson, 2018). The need for inclusive housing encompasses various dimensions, including affordability, and the integration of socially diverse groups, immigrant populations, vulnerable demographics, or those with mental disabilities. A notable development towards addressing these concerns is the integration of "social flats" within projects. These flats are specifically designated for specific collectives and are typically established through collaboration with third-sector associations, such as those supporting women, single young people, or individuals with disabilities. Additionally, fostering typological diversity within buildings represents another avenue towards creating more inclusive environments. This approach allows for different housing units to coexist within the same structure, accommodating diverse needs and preferences while promoting social cohesion and community integration.

3.4 Relationship with the public sector

An integral aspect of the model involves its relationship with the public sector, encompassing both support mechanisms and the qualification of many flats as social housing. Under the grant-of-use model, residents have the long-term right to use housing rather than owing it. What varies for the cases is the ownership - which can be public or cooperative. In cases of public ownership, projects access public land for a specific duration, between 75 and 99 years, provided residents meet social housing requirements. Alternatively, in cases when public land is unavailable or when the conditions imposed by the public sector are not favourable to the group's objectives, groups are purchasing collectively the land, with ownership retained by the cooperative. A common feature across both categories is the decision of the groups to designate all or a portion of the apartments as social housing, aligning with public right-to-housing agendas and fostering public-communitarian collaborations (Ferreri & Vidal, 2021). Qualifying the flats as social housing means that there is economic support from the public sector. The residents should meet specific income criteria and the projects must adhere to regulations regarding apartment sizes, the number of units, and monthly rents. In certain cases, the public character is further demonstrated through the utilization of ground floor spaces for public purposes, enhancing community engagement and contributing to the broader social fabric of the cooperative housing model.

3.5 Neighbourhood impact

A key challenge of cooperative housing projects is their interaction with the surrounding context. As highlighted by Fromm (2012), cooperative housing initiatives have the potential to contribute to neighbourhood repair, and to the social cohesion. One approach involves the repurposing of empty buildings in urban centres, particularly in smaller municipalities, where the community transforms an abandoned building into a new model of cooperative living. This creates the

opportunity to revitalise a degrading neighbourhood and rebuild the social bonds and a sense of community among residents (Jarvis, 2015). Additionally, many groups express a desire to open up spaces within their buildings to the broader neighbourhood, aiming to foster social cohesion and strengthen community ties. This approach not only enriches the cooperative housing experience but also contributes positively to the social fabric of the surrounding area (Williams, 2005).

3.6 Sustainability

From the first initiatives, there was a clear commitment to the creation of more sustainable housing. This is evident in the choice of materials and construction systems used by the cooperative housing projects. Wood structures, compressed earth blocks and passive housing strategies are among the main characteristics of many new buildings, while others focus on rehabilitating existing structures, thereby emphasising sustainability through resource repurposing. Sustainability extends beyond mere construction techniques, encapsulating broader initiatives aimed at reducing consumption. For example, most buildings incorporate common laundry spaces equipped with shared washing machines, thereby promoting resource efficiency. Furthermore, deliberate design choices often include the reduction of private space, fostering a sense of community while concurrently minimising the environmental footprint of construction (Brysch & Czischke, 2021). Finally, the typological flexibility incorporated in many projects permits long-term sustainability. Housing units are designed to be adjustable, enabling residents to continue living in the same building without using more space than needed. Furthermore, the groups understand and design the whole building as their housing, rather than just the apartment that they are using, which allows them to swap apartments within the same building.

4. Conclusion

The emergence and evolution of the grant-of-use cooperative housing model in Catalonia over the last two decades represent a significant development in community-led housing provision and a new paradigm of dwelling. However, to fully grasp its potential, further investigation is needed. This study has identified the primary themes and challenges that are currently confronted by the cooperative housing projects in Catalonia, alongside the diverse mechanisms and practices employed to address them. By delving into these challenges, we glean insights into the transformative capacity of cooperative housing, paving the way for alternative modes of habitation. Our analysis has highlighted key areas such as community living, collaboration, diversity and inclusion, public sector engagement, neighbourhood impact, and sustainability, each bearing significance for the model's success. Comparing experiences, processes and lessons learnt can enrich our understanding of the housing model and contribute to its continual improvement.

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